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Effect Of Forensic Accounting In Managing Corruption In The Nigerian Education Sector

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ABSTRACT

The paper completely condemns the act of corruption in the society. It deeply condemns corruption in the educational sector as it results in an infrastructural deficit that causes a lot of people not to have access to education. Forensic Accounting is the application of specialized knowledge and specific skills to stumble up the pieces of evidence of corruption and fraud that are tenable before a Law Court. The paper was about synergizing the functions of forensic accounting and the efforts of the Nigerian Government to reduce the menace of corruption in the Educational Sector. The study was empirical; data was gathered from the current happenings in the Nigerian Education Sector and past research articles on the level of corruption in the Nigerian Education Sector. This paper recommended among others that the Corruption and Crime-fighting agencies like the EFCC and ICPC should not just employ forensic accounting experts, but should also encourage the government to enact and promulgate a law making it mandatory for all Educational Institutions to include forensic accountants as part of their audit team.

Keywords: Forensic Accounting, Corruption, Educational Sector.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The National Policy on Education (2004) described Education as an instrument of excellence and a tool for economic, social, cultural, and political transformation and development. In addition, the policy made provision for various levels of Education ranging from primary to Tertiary levels to provide the needed manpower that would enhance national development. Dawood (2012) explained that corruption gave birth to National Stagnation which is also visible in the Nigerian education sector. In his view, the evidence of corruption in the Nigerian Education Sector is not far from reach. These can be seen in schools with empty laboratories, outdated teaching and learning materials, poor quality of underpaid teachers, leaking roofs, poor quality chairs, and desks, and a lack of Books in the library (Dawood, 2012). Amimi and Ogbuagwu (2017), reiterated the fact that the existence of corruption in many countries of the world is unquestionable. Lately, this menace has become so popular among Nigerians that its consequences are assuming a worrisome dimension. Corruption is everywhere in Nigeria and touches virtually everything we do in our nation. Ogunfumilakin (2015) described corruption as being severely endemic to public life; and that it has become a contagious disease and one of the major sources of embarrassment to the Nigerian State.

Nigeria is so blessed and unlucky because of its inability to manage its resources courtesy of corruption. The emergence of corruption in the geographical space of Nigeria has become troublesome as it has shown itself in many ways which include, election rigging, extortion by the Police, Ghost workers syndrome, contract falsification, embezzlement, and forgery of all kinds. It is very painful that corruption

has debarred Nigeria from competing favorably with its counterparts like the Asian nations of Malaysia, Indonesia, and Singapore, despite all our God-given resources. Douglas and Magdalene (2017) posit that corruption in any of its different forms has very dangerous potential that weakens and brings to nothing the developmental plans of honest and hardworking institutions and individuals in the nation. It also has the possibility of discouraging foreign direct investment and bringing down the foundation of the value system upon which the sustainable development of a nation and its citizens is laid. Ajie and Wokekoro (2012) in their study explained that corruption is a culture in Nigeria with the various major ethnic groups having their dialectical slangs for corruption. This is seen by the Igbos as “*Akaazu*”; Yoruba as “*Egunje*”; and the Hausas as “*Chauchau*”.

Pierre (2014) argued that the main factors encouraging corrupt behavior in Education Sector includes the poor salaries earned by Education workers and general poverty. It therefore means that the Poorer the nation, the higher the level of corruption and vice versa (Pierre, 2014). A detailed review of literatures suggests that there are very few literatures that explained the issue of Education and corruption in detail. Therefore, it is very visible that carrying out a study in the sphere of corruption in the area of Education should be regarded as a major priority to be looked upon. This paper is therefore imperative because it seeks to give a narrative about the endemic effects of corruption on the Nigerian educational system. It will cover all the levels of Education starting from the primary through secondary to the tertiary levels. The main emphasis would be on highlighting the problems of corruption in Nigeria Education Sector and also proffering solution.

1.2 METHODOLOGY

The method adopted for this study is Philosophical. Nwaokugha and Danladi (2010) explained that Philosophical method involves the critical examination of concepts and prepositions of a study with the intention of clarifying all possible meanings associated with them. (Nwaokugha & Danladi; 2010).

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The Concept of Corruption

It is believed that the major factors that have made corruption to evolve in developing countries emanates from the conflict between traditional values and the imported norms that came with modernization and socio-political and economic development (Pierre, 2014). According to the concise Oxford English Dictionary, corruption is defined as putridity, taint, debasement, venality, rottenness and immorality. This definition sees everything that is bad as corruption. Ogunfumilakin (2015) have stressed that corruption has permeated every sector of the Nigerian society. This is visible as many African nations are endowed with abundant mineral and natural resources, yet a great percentage of its inhabitants live in abject poverty with Nigeria leading in the corruption rating index (Ogunfumilakin, 2015).

The Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Crimes Commission (ICPC) Act (2003) Section 2 has described corruption to include vices such as fraud, bribery and other related Crimes and offences. Corruption has also been viewed by many experts as the abuse of position and power of trust on personal in collective ground. Corruption has also been blamed for the consistent subversion of Justice and equality. It is instrumental to the erosion of confidence in Nigerian democratic process and has relegated the spirit of patriotism among Nigerians to the background. It is however, a known fact that one of the strongest contributions to underdevelopment in Nigeria is corruption. The United Nations Global Programme against Corruption (GPAC) defined corruption as the abuse of power for private gain. Also, the Transparency International referred to corruption as abuse of entrusted power for private gain. Farida (2009) reaffirmed this definition by explaining that corruption is the pervasion or change from the general accepted rules or laws for selfish gain (Farida, 2010). Douglas and Magdalene (2017) have described corruption as a hydra-headed scourge that has gained high profile and epidemic proportion so known and contagious that its seals and impressions can be seen and felt by people in all countries of the world

(Douglas and Magdaline, 2017). As noted by Okeyin, Ejue and Ekanem (2013), corruption has assumed a great dimension that it has become pervasive and destructive to the very foundation of Nigeria stability (Okeyin, Ejue and Ekanem, 2013). In the last decade, virtually every year Nigeria has either been ranked as the most corrupt nation or the second most corrupt nation in the world by the Transparency International Corruption Index. Corruption in Nigeria is likened to cancer, the more you try to eradicate it, the more it spreads. Be it as it may, there are areas where the existence of corruption can be more damaging. One of these areas is Education. Corruption in Educational Sector can be detrimental to the growth and development of the Nigerian state. That is why this paper shall x-ray the consequences of corruption in the Educational Industry for Nigeria growth. In doing this, the study will identify the trends and shapes of corruption in the Nigeria Educational sector and proffer remarkable solutions to tame the menace for a better Nigeria Educational System.

2.2 Nigerian Society and Corruption

One of the main threats to the Socio-economic and political growth and development of Nigeria is corruption. Corruption is expressed in diverse forms in Nigeria ranging from sex for marks in the academia to extortion from passengers and drivers by Police. Others are bribery, abuse of office for private gains, ghost workers syndrome, contract inflation, oil black market, racketeering, having special examination centers, examination malpractices, fake marriages to get residents permits, child and human trafficking, smuggling of goods into the country without paying duties, manufacturing, distribution and sale of fake and substandard drugs and products, forgery of land documents, inflation of transport fares etc.

Amina and Ogbuagwu (2017) are of the view that corruption in Africa is led by Nigeria as evidenced in so many indices. For instance, Nigeria with a current population of close to 200 million people has been adjudged to be corrupt in all facets of its social life. Accordingly, this allusion has been proven by various rankings attributed to Nigeria in the past years and recently by the Transparency International (TI) (Amimi & Ogbugwu, 2017). Okoye, Mamiako, Jugu and Jat(2017) have argued that in spite of the damaging effects of corruption to a third world country like Nigeria, and indeed in most African countries, corruption is often glamorized thereby making enemies of anti-corruption crusaders. They further allude that it is however unfortunate that this dreaded monster tends to trickle down from the top of the Nigeria society (Okoye, Maimako, Jugu and Jet; 2017).

2.3 Global Index for Measuring Corruption.

The emergence of corruption and corrupt practices and its negative effects on the socio-political and economic development of economies of the world, has attracted the attention of global political actors, including those in the private and public sectors. Before now, there was no need to measure corruption index as the effects of corruption was not as dangerous as it is today. However, it is now possible to measure corruption as they exist several survey based measures to assess the level of corruption in the different countries of the world. Some of these measures include Transparency International Index, Global Competitive Report Index (GCRI) etc. It is a well-known facts that transparency International is a worldwide organization fighting the scourge of corruption. It is based in Berlin, Germany. This body makes use of corruption perception index to assess the level of corruption in every nation of the world. It measures index ranges from 0 (highly corrupt) and 100 (Free from corruption). However, no country has been able to score 100 in the world implying that corruption is virtually in existence in every country of the world today.

2.4 The Nigerian Educational System

Education is the process of facilitating learning, or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs and habits. It is the act or process of imparting or acquiring general knowledge, developing the powers of reasoning and judgment, and generally of preparing oneself or others intellectually for mature life. Nigeria runs a Federation system; therefore, the Nigerian education system is controlled and coordinated

by a Federal Minister of Education. This Education Ministry makes policies and programs that drive the Nigerian Educational Sector (Wikipedia, 2019).

The Nigerian National Educational Policy (2004) set out goals for the Nigerian Education System. There goals are listed below:-

1. Free and Democratic System
2. Ensure Great and dynamic economy
3. Just and egalitarian society and
4. A land full of bright opportunity for all.

These are the main goals set by the policy for primary, secondary and tertiary education. The education policy's major aim is to ensure national development. The Nigerian education is entrusted with the mandate of putting the nation in the right direction so as to effectively achieve the socio-political and economic goals of the country.

Corruption and corrupt acts in the educational system pose great threat to the achievement of the laid down goals set by the educational policies. Corruption in education has consistently set the roadmap for the country's inability to attain sustainable development through education. The virus called corruption has drastically reduced the efficiency and the effectiveness of the resources meant for the growth and development of the Nigeria Educational Sector.

According to the African Union (AU), African countries losses about 25% of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) to corruption and corruption related activities. Corruption in Education has been described as the act of using public office and position for personal aggrandizement and benefits to the advantage of Education Officers.

2.5 Corruption: Defined

In its 2008 corruption glossary report, Transparency International described corruption as the abuse of entrusted power for private gain. Furthermore, it classified corruption as either petty, grand or political. Grand corruption consist of acts committed at a high level of government that distributes policies for the central functioning of the state, enabling leaders to benefit at the expense of the public good. However, petty corruption has been described as everyday abuse of entrusted power by low and mid-level public officials in their interaction with ordinary citizens. Political corruption is a manipulation of policies, institutions and rules procedure in the allocation of resources and financing by political decision-makers, who abuse their position to sustain their power, status, and wealth (Transparency International, 2018). Douglas and Magdalene (2017) argued that the features of corruption help to make discussions that are focused on corruption more elastic and robust because a feature of corruption in one country that is absent in another can help in illuminating more light on low people in another country or culture perceive the problem of corruption to be (Douglas & Magdalene,2017).

Khan(1996) sees corruption as the incorporation of any act that deviates from those rules and regulations that govern the behavior and actions of any person in a position of authority, especially actions that turn such privilege into avenues for personal and privately amassing of wealth, power and authority(Khan,1996). Lawal and Tobi(2006), contributed by defining corruption as any conscious attempt or deliberate diversion of resources from satisfaction of the general interest to that of selfish personal interest (Lawal & Tobi,2006). On the other hand, Ojude(2000) had a more inclusive definition of corruption when he defined corruption as any systematic vice perpetuated by individuals, society, or state in general, where not too good concepts for equality, social harmony, and harmonious living –e.g. Favoritism, Nepotism, Tribalism, Sectionalism, undue enrichment, amassing of wealth, abuse of office, power, position, etc become norms, a lifestyle of the people and the State(Ojude,2000). Ogunfumlakin (2015), posited that corruption is an unindicted attitude and manner within an organization set up that can falsify the integrity, purpose, and goal of such an organization. Corruption subverts justice and equality, erodes confidence in the democratic system, and makes the development of patriotic spirit impossible.

Corruption has significantly contributed to the emergence of poverty, hunger, and under-development suffered by the Nigerian people (Ogunfumlakin, 2015).

2.5.1 What is Education Corruption?

As already explained in some parts of this study, corruption simply includes the abuse of authority for material and personal gain. But considering the relevance of education to the livelihood of a nation, hence the definition of education corruption encompasses the abuse of power and authority for material as well as personal gain. Pierre (2014) is of the view that corruption in education expresses itself in four ways. These includes (i) Through its education function (ii) Through the supply of goods and services (iii) through professional misconduct and (iv) The treatment of taxation and property (Pierre, 2014).

2.5 Education Corruption through Supply of Goods and Services

It is very obvious that education in any country is a massive business enterprise. The schools and students need to be supplied with infrastructure and other relevant learning materials. The supplies of these goods have long been monopolized by the government, thus the value of the goods supplied is often far less than the amount budgeted and approved. The missing monies accruing from the gap arising from poor supplies are cornered for private purposes of government education administrators.

2.5.2 Education Corruption through Professional Misconduct.

Many forms of professional misconduct include corruption in the education sector of Nigeria. Among the most common are:-

- (i) Accepting material gifts and rewards in exchange for positive grades, assessment in selection to specialized program.
- (ii) Sex for grade- a major cause of concern in Nigeria higher institution of learning.
- (iii) Biasing a grade or an assessment because of a private request.
- (iv) Accessing of grade on assessment biased by a student’s race, culture, social class, ethnicity, or other unreasonable attributes.

2.6 Types of Opportunities of Corruption in Nigerian Education Sector

It is evident that in the educational sector of any economy if corruption and fraud practices are not properly checked and nipped in the bud, it may develop into a full corruption lifestyle capable of discrediting the entire education sector and activities of the country. In this section of the paper, we shall enumerate the major areas of corruption in educational supplies and the administration of human and material resources in the educational sector of Nigeria.

Table 1

Areas	Corrupt Practices	Impact on Education
School building Rehabilitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fraud in public tendering • Embezzlement • School mapping 	Access, Quality, Bad location of school
Equipment, Textbook, Food	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fraud in public tendering • Embezzlement • Bypass of criteria 	Equity, quality School meals free form the rich and not available for the poor.
Teacher Appointment/Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Favoritism • Nepotism • Bribes 	Less qualified teachers
Teacher Behavior	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ghost Teachers • Bribes for school entrance examination, assessment and private tutoring 	Disparity in staffing by schools, discrimination against the poor.
Examinations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selling of information • Favoritism • Nepotism • Bribes 	Unjustified credentials available to students who can afford to pay bribes.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic Fraud 	
Information Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manipulating data • Selecting and suppressing information 	Omitting data on repetition drop out
Finance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transgressing rules/procedure • Inflation of costs and activities • Leakages of funds 	Less resource for quality Textbooks and other learning materials.

Source: Ogunfumilakin (2015)

Table 2: Major Opportunities for Corruption in Area of Educational Planning and Management

Areas of Planning /Management	Major Opportunities for Corrupt Practices
Finance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transparency rules and procedures /by pass of criteria • Inflation of cost and activities • Embezzlement
Allocation of specific allowances (fellowships, subsidies etc)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Favoritism /nepotism • Bribes • By pass of criteria • Discrimination (political, social, ethics)
Construction, maintenance and school repairs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fraud in public tendering (pay offs, gifts) • Collusion among suppliers • Embezzlement • Manipulating data • Ghost deliveries
Distribution of equipment, furniture and materials e.g. Textbooks, school meal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fraud in public tendering • Collusion among suppliers • Embezzlement • Purchase of unnecessary equipment • By pass of allocation criteria
Writing of Textbooks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fraud in selection of authors (Favoritism) • By pass of copyright laws • Students forced to purchase materials • Copy righted by instructors
Teachers appointed, management (Transfer, promotion) payment and training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fraud in the appointment and deployment of teachers (Favoritism, bribes) • Discrimination (political, social ethnic) • Falsification of credentials, use of fake Diplomas • Pay delay, sometimes with unauthorized deductions
Teachers Behavior (Professional misconduct)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ghost teachers • Absenteeism • Illegal fees (for school entrance exams) • Favoritism/nepotism/acceptance of gift • Several investment in exploitation
Institutions Accreditation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fraud in Accreditation process (Favoritism, bribes, gifts)

Source: Corrupt schools, corrupt universities; what can be done, Paris International Institute for Educational Planning cited in Ogunfumilakin (2015)

2.7 Major causes of corruption in Nigeria Education Sector

It has been mentioned in different fora's that education is a very big business in Nigeria. However, one major problem that has impeded the growth of education in Nigeria is corruption. Research has shown that there are several factors responsible for the rise in corruption in the educational sector of Nigeria. Some of these include:

1. **School officials and personnel:** one major factor that has affected the process of monitoring school activities by stakeholders is bribery. This corrupt practice has led to admission of excess student through the use of kick-backs especially in the University environment.
2. **Lack of quality supervision:** The human resources in our schools ought to be properly supervised for effective service delivery. But because of corruption and kick-backs, this practice is not effectively affected.
3. **Government contract manipulation:** All areas of government, officials responsible for procurement of schools materials falsify receipts and even supply sub-standard equipment and materials to the schools. This in-turn will have grave negative effects in our schools.
4. **Poor release of funds:** Due to value misplacement by the government, it has become the order of the day for the government to underfund the educational sector. This has also expressed itself in the neglect of staff welfare, thus giving room for breeding of corruption.
5. **Parental factor:** When parents encourage their wards to engage in examinations malpractice by even supervising the whole process, it leaves behind a lot to imagine that so called leaders of tomorrow are building on a faulty foundation.

2.8 Concept of Forensic Accounting

In his essay titled "Forensic Accounting: its place in today's economy" Maurice E. Pelubet set the pace for the introduction of the concept of forensic accounting. By the late 1940s, forensic accounting had become popular in some part of the world. However, it was until the 1980s that some researchers started to finally discuss forensic accounting and its uses in research activities around the world (Rassey, 2009). Accordingly, some western nations like the USA began to formally consider it as a new field of accounting. Ozkul and Panuke, 2012 are of the view that the field of forensic accounting composed mainly of accounting, auditing and investigative skills (Ozkul and Panuke, 2012). The word forensic has been adduced to mean suitable for use in the Court of Law. Crumbley (2005) in his definition of forensic accounting as an act of identifying, recording, settling, extracting, sorting, reporting and verifying past financial data or other accounting activities for settling current or prospective legal disputes in using such past financial data to settle disputes (Crumbley, 2005). In their contribution, Melita and Mathew (2007) argued that forensic accounting basically has to do with a financial detective with a suspicious mind, a financial blood hound, one with a "sixth sense" and critical thinking ability that would lead to reconstruction and re-analysis of accounting and financial transaction and events and an individual who looks beyond the numbers (Melita & Mathew, 2007).

2.9 Forensic Accounting and Reduction of Corruption in the Nigerian Education Sector

It is obvious by now that a whole lot of writers and researches in the field of forensic accounting have put forward forensic accounting as a veritable solution to many fraudulent and corrupt scenarios in Nigeria. For instance, Onwodi, Okafor and Onyali (2015) are of the view that forensic accounting skills are badly needed because of the rising level of financial crimes in all facets of the Nigerian economy. More so, according to Mukowo Ogijo & Faboyede(2013), the criteria for a forensic accountant to be successful is for he/she to be one who always seeks to know the detail and persistent and ambitious to get to the root of a financial crime case. Other researchers like D. Gabriele (2009) allude to the fact that a forensic accountant must possess analytical proficiency, legal knowledge and must have the ability to differentiate between opinion and facts; and possess both oral and written communication skills if he/she must be a profficient and successful forensic accountant anywhere (D.Gabriele,2009).

According to the Federal Bureau of Investigation (2012) and Oseni (2017) as cited in Ibiduni; Ibiduni, Okere and Awo (2018), forensic accountant carryout the following functions:

- i) Conducting through forensic financial analysis of business and personal records and also developing financial profiles of individuals or groups identified as participating in suspicious or illegal activity;
- ii) Identifying and tracing funding sources and interrelated transactions;
- iii) Participating in gathering evidence and preparing search warrants (Affidavits associated with financial analysis).
- iv) Accompanying case agents on interviews of subjects and key witnesses in secure and non-confrontational settings; and compiling findings and conclusions into financial investigative reports and meetings with persecuting attorneys to discuss strategies and other litigation support functions.

Abayomi (2011) is of the opinion that corruption is a deadly cancer, and the only solution to curbing this cancer in Nigeria is for every citizen to embrace transparency, integrity and accountability in all their private and public dealings. However, he also alluded that the root of corruption has taken a firm position in the country to the point that the corruption fighting indices of transparency, accountability and integrity have all lost their place in the Nigerian state of affairs.

Accordingly, one major way that forensic accounting can curb corruption in the Nigerian education sector is by ensuring that forensic accounting experts are employed and allowed to perform their functions in all transactions concerning the Nigerian educational sector. If forensic audit is carried out on one or more cases of corruption in the educational system in Nigeria, it would go a long way in deterring others from siphoning the scarce resources and funds meant for the development of the Nigerian educational sector.

2.10 Reasons why Nigeria must be free from Educational Corruption.

It is generally agreed that what makes a nation great lies on how it chooses its political, commercial and technical leaders. Generally, it has been affirmed that no modern nation can survive and succeed if its leaders are chosen from an educational system with a corrupt foundation. Education provides the mechanism through which leaders who can make great impact on a nation's development can emerge. Education is a common instrument used by nations to refine their potential leaders who in-turn will help create a great and enviable nation.

Taking Nigeria as a case study, there is need for our educational sector to be free from corruption. Owing to the fact that our rich abundant natural resources notwithstanding, there cannot be taped and harnessed for the good of all if the leaders are corrupt. Therefore, knowing fully that the educational sector is the breeding ground for future leaders, all hands must be on deck to sever the relationship that corruption has with education in Nigeria. We can do this by entrenching honesty, transparency, accountability and probity in the transactions and dealings that affects the Nigerian educational system.

Forensic accounting reduces corruption in the education sector by applying investigative techniques to detect and prevent financial crimes like fraud and embezzlement, thereby increasing transparency, ensuring accountability, and resolving corrupt practices. Establishing specialized forensic accounting units and prosecuting offenders are recommended to enhance public trust and improve financial integrity within educational institutions.

2.11 The Characteristics of Nigerian Education System Free from Corruption.

A Nigerian Education Sector that is free from corruption would have the following characteristics:

- Equality of access to educational opportunities
- Fairness in the distribution of educational curriculum and materials
- Fairness and transparency in the selection and employment of Teachers and lecturers.
- Fairness and transparency in the award and execution of education related contracts.
- Fairness in accreditation in which all institutions are judged by professional standards equally applied and opens to public.

- Fairness in the procurement and acquisition of educational goods and services; and
- Maintenance of professional standards of conflict by those who administer educational institutions and who teach them whether in public or private institutions in Nigeria.

3.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

From the review of this paper, the following recommendations were arrived at:-

1. The crime and corruption fighting institutions in Nigeria should endeavor to apply forensic science technique in unraveling the monumental corruption taking place in the Nigerian educational sector. What this means is that ICPC and EFCC must work hand in hand with Forensic Accountants.
2. Just as enumerated in the body of this paper, Forensic accountants in Nigeria must be creative and competent to and constantly enlightened about the happenings in the educational sector so as to promptly nip in the bud any act of corruption.
3. To improve the Nigerian educational sector, the forensic accountants, should not just be invited when there is a corruption case to investigate, there should be a deliberate law mandating all government and private education institutions in Nigeria to make forensic accountants part of their audit team.
4. The Government must take decisive action against education administrators and officers who are involved in Educational corruption and fraud to serve as deterrent to others.
5. Finally, the forensic accountants association in conjunction with the government should set up preventive measures specific to education corruption such as:
 - i) Structural reforms necessary to reduce the opportunity for corruption.
 - ii) Measures necessary to actually prevent corruption; and
 - iii) Measures to sanction or denote or punish infractions on the part of educational administrators when it occurs.

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